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SBRT without HT is a validated option for low and favorable intermediate risk prostate cancer?

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Prostate cancer (PCa) is the leading cause of cancer in men and the leading cause of death among malignancy causing disability worldwide with its high incidence, high cure rate, and treatment-associated morbidity. In the developed world most patients with PCa receive a diagnosis of clinically localized disease, and the majority have low-risk or intermediate-risk disease as defined by the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) guidelines. There is no strong bias regarding ADT for low and favourable intermediate-risk prostate cancer patients receiving SBRT in the growing volume of retrospective data.

Stereotactic body radiotherapy (SBRT), or extreme hypofractionation, is a specific form of EBRT in which advanced radiotherapy techniques are used to deliver very large doses of radiation per fraction. PCa has a unique radiobiological feature, namely the relatively slow proliferation, characterized by a low α/β ratio compared to the normal organs around the target (Brenner and Hall 1999; Fowler et al. 2003). According to the characteristic, extreme hypofractionated radiotherapy would offer favourable tumor control without increasing risk of late toxicity.

Androgen deprivation therapy (ADT) is beneficial for unfavorable intermediate-risk (IR) prostate cancer patients receiving curative radiotherapy (RT). However, for favorable IR patients and low risk patients the latest NCCN guidelines recommends RT alone. The NCCN guidelines continue to state that "longer follow-up and prospective multi-institutional data are required to evaluate longer-term results regarding SBRT" as a treatment option for this group of patients.

Keywords: Prostate cancer, SBRT, Androgen deprivation therapy

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